

International Peer Review Journal

p-ISSN 1817-5562

e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)

CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

**The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine
The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health
and Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists
International Panel**

Volume 7 Number 1 April 2011

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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www.newiraqim.4t.com

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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The Evolution of Modern Healthcare and Health Education In Iraq

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The N Iraqi J Med, April 2011; 7(1):72-80

The aim of this paper is to provide a description of the evolution of modern health care and medical and health education in Iraq based largely on official governmental papers and documents.

The healthcare and health services were seriously bad during the Ottoman reign. The few hospitals established didn't meet the public demands. After the World War I, Iraq passed from the failing Ottoman Empire to the British control. Many of these hospitals were damaged during the First World War. During the British occupation the British army directorate of health affairs provided health service to people in Basra most probably in attempt to reduce the exposure of the British army to the diseases in the region. That health directorate was organized by colonel Batty who was appointed as the administrative chief.

On 11 November 1920 what is known as Mesopotamia became a League of Nations

mandate under British control with the name "State of Iraq". Emir (Prince) Faisal, leader of the Arab revolt against the Ottoman sultan during the Great War, and member of the Hashemite family from Mecca, became the first king of the new state. He obtained the throne partly by the influence of T. E. Lawrence. Although the monarch was legitimized and proclaimed King by a plebiscite in 1921, nominal independence was only achieved in 1932, when the British Mandate officially ended.⁽¹⁻³⁾

The formation of National governance in Iraq with establishment of the Hashemite Kingdom in the 23rd of August 1921 was associated with beginning of the evolution of modern healthcare and health in Iraq.⁽¹⁻³⁾ The first Iraqi Ministry of Health was established and Dr Hanna Al Khaiat (1884-1959) was the first Iraqi Minister of Health. However, during the same year the country witnessed serious economic crises which led to abolishing the Ministry of health and converting its structure into a general health directorate affiliated to the Ministry of Internal affairs. Several useful health laws were issued during the 1920s such as the small pox vaccination law.⁽⁴⁾

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During 1922 there were 65 physicians in Iraq (1 doctor of every 28000 of the population), 86 nurse .These numbers increased to 241 doctors , 81of them were Iraqi doctors (1 doctor for ever 11717 of the population) and 200 nurses in 1932.

In 1939 the affiliation of the general health directorate moved to the newly formed Ministry of Social Affairs. The early evolution of modern healthcare was associated with establishment of several hospitals. The Royal Hospital in Bab Al Muadham which was established in 1925 the most important one.

The general health directorate was gradually growing. In 1951 the general health directorate was consisting of 3 main parts; The divan of public health directorate, the administration of Liwas health, and the deanery of medical college.⁽⁵⁾ The divan of public health directorate was consisting of five main directorates and 7 sections including section of nursing affairs, accountancy section, and an other 5 managerial sections.

The five directorates affiliated with the divan of public health included:

1. Directorate of preventive and social medicine which was concerned with prevention of endemic and epidemic diseases including venereal and

respiratory diseases. This directorate established quarantines.

2. Directorate of curative medicine concerned with management of hospitals, health centers and clinics, and supervising pharmacies and medical stores. Directorate of curative medicine was also supervising technical institutes (Pathology institute, Bacteriology institute, Forensic medicine institute, Radiology institute, Chemical laboratory institute, and endemic diseases institute)
3. Directorate of Inspection
4. Directorate of statistics.
5. Capital Health directorate.

Figure-1 shows the structure of the general health directorate late in 1951.

During that time Iraq was divided into 14 administrative parts called Liwa. In each Liwa there was a chief of health in charge of the health services in the Liwa. The administration of Liwas health consisted of the 13 Liwa (with exception of the capital) health chiefs and their assistants who are physicians.

Figure (1): The structure of the general health directorate late in 1951.

During the 1940s there were 10 fully equipped hospitals in Iraq; 7 in Baghdad and 1 in Mosul, Basra and Kirkuk. There were also 41 poorly equipped hospitals distributed in the 13 Liwas other than Baghdad.⁽⁷⁾

After 1952, the Iraqi Ministry of Health (1951) was re-established again according to the law 28 for the year 1952 and the affiliation of the already established general health directorate and the College of Medicine moved from the Ministry of Social Affairs to the newly formed Iraqi Ministry of Health.^(7, 8) Abdul Rahman Jawdat was appointed as the Minister of Health. The three main missions of the Iraqi Ministry of Health were stated in the law 28 for the year 1952:

1. Providing public health care.
2. Establishing prevention institutions and hospitals.
3. Supervisions on the Iraqi Medical College and its teaching hospital medical colleges, schools, hospitals and

health institutions that will be formed in the future.

According to the Law 28 for the year 1952 several regulations were issued to determine the structure of the Iraqi Ministry of Health and its related hospitals, institutions, colleges and schools.

The first Ministerial regulation was issued under number 26 for year 1956 stated that the Minister of health is the supreme president of the Iraqi Ministry of Health and in charge of its duties and all ministerial decisions and orders are issued under his command and supervision.⁽⁹⁾ The structure of the Iraqi Ministry of Health after 1952 consisted of 3 main administrative parts: The divan of the ministry of health, the deanery of the medical college and the general health inspectorship as shown in table-1.⁽⁹⁾ Two directorates and 4 management sections including accountant and legal sections were affiliated to the Divan of the Ministry of Health.⁽⁹⁾

Table(1: The structure of the Iraqi Ministry of Health in 1956

The divan of the ministry of health

The directorate of curative medicine:

1. Department of hospitals, clinics, and pharmacies.
2. Department of rural health
3. Department of technical institutions (Pathology institute, Bacteriology institute, Vaccine institute, Radiology institute, Chemical laboratory institute, Research institute, and Pasteur institute)
4. Department of medical stores

The directorate of preventive and social health:

1. Department of endemic diseases which includes malaria section, Ankylostoma section, bilharzias section, leprosy section and insect annihilation section.
2. Department of public health and nutrition monitoring
3. Department of social health which includes childhood and maternity section, respiratory diseases section, skin and venereal diseases section and health propaganda section.
4. Department of quarantines and epidemics.
5. Department of health and biostatistics.
6. Department of registration.

Four management sections

The deanery of the medical college

1. College of Medicine
2. College of Pharmacy and chemistry.
3. Nursing and Midwifery school.
4. School of health employees
5. The Royal Hospital of Baghdad.

The general health inspectorship

The Dean of the Deanery was under the minister of health and he appoints a director to manage each college and school.

In 1956, the Iraqi Ministry of Health was expanded and re-arranged and its organizing structure was changed according to the law 26 for the year 1956.⁽¹⁰⁾ The structure of the Iraqi

Ministry of Health in 1956 consisted of 4 main administrative parts: The directorate of general health, the deanery of the medical college and the directorate general inspectorship, and the general directorate of medical appliances as shown in table-2.

Table(2): The structure of the Iraqi Ministry of Health in 1956

The directorate of general health (17 directorates):	11. Directorate of biostatistics
1. Directorate of general health for curative medicine	12. Directorate of international health
2. Directorate of general health for preventive and social medicine	13. Directorate of dairy project
3. Directorate of forensic medicine.	14. Directorate of health engineering
4. Directorate of student health.	15. Directorate of hospital engineering
5. Directorate of chemical laboratory.	16. Directorate of blood bank
6. Directorate of eradication of tuberculosis.	17. Directorate of legal affairs
7. Directorate of maternity and childhood care.	The deanery of the medical college
8. Directorate of venereal diseases.	College of medicine
9. Directorate of preventive health	College of pharmacy
10. Directorate of technical institutes (Pathology institute, Bacteriology, Pasture, small pox vaccine institute, Radiology institute, Nutritional Research institute, and endemic diseases institute)	College of Dentistry
	School of health employees
	Nursing and midwifery school
	The directorate general inspectorship
	The general directorate of medical appliances

In 1956 the Iraqi ministry of health established the supreme health council to help the minister in approving general health projects and establish the necessary bases to improve the level of health in the country.⁽¹¹⁾ The council included the dean of medical college, the directors general of the health directorates and their deputies in addition to 4 specialist physicians.

The divan of the ministry of health which was removed from the organizing structure was restored in 1958 to include the directorate of general health services, the general directorate of preventive health, the directorate of general medical appliances, the general health inspectorship and the special office.

The new agreements with oil companies signed in 1952 and in the 6th of December 1955 was associated with an increase in oil revenues from 13.3 millions to 86.9 millions Iraqi Dinars in 1958. This increase in oil revenues was associated with an increase in the health budget during the 1950s. Table-3 shows the health expenditure during the years 1948-1957 and the percentage of health budget from the

national budget.^(12, 13) It's interesting to note that during these years the ministry of defense and police budget was 39% of the country expenditures.

Table (3): The health expenditures during the years 1948-1957 and budget percentage from the national budget

The Year	itures in Iraqi Dinars, Budget(%) from national budget
1948	1156577 (4.8%)
1949	1300000(4.4%)
1950	1829198 (6.2%)
1951	2341868 (7.5%)
1952	2973849 (5.6%)
1953	2973849 (5.6%)
1954	379458 (7%)
1955	4327158 (9)
1956	4996728 (7.1%)
1957	4862000 (6.6)

In April 1948 the WHO was established and Iraq joined the organization. In March 25, 1952 Iraq government signed a technical aid agreement with WHO. This agreement made the services of international health experts available for Iraq. In addition according to the

agreement the WHO organized workshops and training courses for Iraq. This agreement also helped Iraq to establish the BCG vaccination program.

The evolution of the health educational institutions, the evolution of health care in Iraq was associated with evolution of the health educational institutions. The deanery of the medical college emerged in association with ministry of health and the general health directorate during the 1920s. The deanery of medical college included the college of medicine, college of pharmacy, college of health employees and nursing and midwifery school.⁽¹⁴⁾ The college of deanery was added in 1953. The dean of the deanery is immediately under the minister of health and he appoint a director for each college or school who should be approved by the minister of health.

The Iraqi medical college which was affiliated to the ministry of health and the general health directorate earlier was connected academically to the University of Aal Al Bait. The college was opened on the 29th of December 1927. The College was following the rules and regulation of the Ministry of Knowledge. The lectures were initially given in building of the Royal Hospital. On the 4th of April 1930 the Royal College moved to its building in Bab Al Muadham near the Royal Hospital. Entry to the college requires a

graduation from secondary school in the science branch. The 6-year curriculum was very similar to the curriculum of the University of Edinburgh. In 1927 twenty students were enrolled in the college, the number increased to 80 in 1950. In 1932, 12 students graduated from the college and 24 in 1933. In 1934 there were a total of 73 students graduated from the college. Table-4 shows the number of graduates of the colleges and schools of the Deanery during the years from 1949 to 1958.

The college of pharmacy and chemistry which was established in 1922 was abolished in April 1936 to be re-established again on modern bases in October 1936 and 21 students were enrolled for the first year [1]. On the 3rd of January the first regulation of the college was issued. The regulation defined in 28 items the administrative structure, the admission criteria, examinations and punishments. Initially a 4-year curriculum was taught in English but the study period was extended to 5 years in 1945 to include training I pharmacies (9 months in private pharmacies and 3 months in government pharmacies), However the training year was later modified to 9 months with five hours spent in the morning in government pharmacies and 3 hours in the afternoon spent in private pharmacies. In 1940 the college of pharmacy graduated 12 pharmacists.^(14, 16)

Table (4): The number of graduates of the colleges and schools of the Deanery during the years from 1949 to 1958.

Graduation Year	College of Medicine	College of Pharmacy	College of Chemistry	School of health employee	School of Nursing and Midwifery
1949	44	2	—	30	25
1950	23	11	—	17	29
1951	46	16	7	30	25
1952	40	10	12	35	25
1953	44	20	8	42	25
1954	50	14	2	35	47
1955	67	17	6	42	40
1956	78	23	3	39	83
1957	51	33	Close[]	49	77
1958	75	29	—	25	79

In 1953 the college of dentistry was established and the regulation of the college was issued which determined the administrative structure. Initially the study was 4 years but was extended later to 5 years. In 1953 15 students were enrolled. The college enrolled graduate of secondary schools the

scientific branch. 65 students were enrolled in 1954. In 1958 the college graduated 21 students including 6 females.⁽¹⁷⁾

The school of health employee was established in 1932 with aim of graduating assistant physicians, assistant pharmacists and technical nurses. The school enrolled graduates

of the intermediary schools and study period was 3 years including 1 year training in governmental hospitals.^(15, 18)

Nursing and Midwifery school was established in 1936 and was managed initially by Irish chief nurse miss Kinelston. The school enrolled graduate of primary schools. The study period was 3 years. The school established a 1-year postgraduate training program in obstetrics and midwifery after completing the training the trainee became a certified midwife. In 1950 the school graduated a total of 1360 nurse and 28 certified midwife.⁽¹⁸⁾

Endemic and epidemic diseases: During the evolution of healthcare in Iraq during the periods from 1921 to 1945 the health authorities was not able to overcome the problems of endemic diseases which was associated with significant mortality. The lack of experts and specialized health cadres, poor health budget and the absence of a central health policy to eradicate endemic diseases were the main contributing factors to that failure. Failure of preventive health care during that period made the health authorities concentrating on curative medical care. However, during the period from 1948 to 1958 the establishment of the Institute of Endemic Diseases contributed to improvement in preventive care. In addition the agreements between Iraq and UNICEF and WHO helped in the control of many endemic disease such as malaria, Bejel, cholera and plague. However, tuberculosis, trachoma and ankylostoma infection remained out of control.⁽¹⁸⁻²⁸⁾ High prevalence of illiteracy and poverty was the main factors precluded the control of these endemic diseases.

Malaria was at the top of endemic diseases in Iraq.^(18, 19) Urinary tract Bilharziasis was the second most important health problem in Iraq after malaria.^(20,21,22,23) Table-5 shows the numbers of the registered cases of the important endemic diseases in Iraq during the 1940s and 1950s.⁽¹⁹⁻²⁸⁾ According to the data available from laboratory tests made on 1056 pupils in Basra, 230 (32%) pupils were affected with Bilharziasis. It was estimated that 26% of Iraqi school children were affected with Bilharziasis.^(21,24) Failure of the local health

authorities to control Bilharziasis led the government made agreement with WHO to help in the control of the diseases in 1956. The WHO team examined 40734 school children and found that 8608 children were infected with bilharzias.^(20, 24, 25)

Trachoma was the third most important endemic disease during the first four decades of the evolution of modern health care in Iraq.^(25,26) Other forms of bacterial conjunctivitis was also prevalent. In 1951 there were 20434 registered cases of bacterial conjunctivitis (240/10.000 population, while in 1952 there were 27523 cases (256/100.000 population).⁽²⁷⁾ Venereal diseases (syphilis, soft chancre and gonorrhoea) were also endemic and up to 90% of them were attributed to prostitution.⁽²⁷⁾ During the year 1954 about 51.5% of the cases of gonorrhoea and 49.4% of the cases of syphilis were registered in Baghdad. Basra was second to Baghdad in prevalence 18.9 % of the cases of gonorrhoea and 25.4% of the cases of syphilis having while Mosul ranked third with 8.5 % of the cases of gonorrhoea and 2.4% of the cases of syphilis.⁽²⁹⁾

Bejel or endemic syphilis which is a chronic skin and tissue disease caused by infection by a subspecies of the spirochete *Treponema pallidum* was also endemic in Iraq. It was estimated that Bejel affected about 500000 Iraqi early during the 1950s accounting for 10% of the Iraq population during that time.^(18, 27) Ankylostoma infection was also endemic and was especially affecting peasants decreasing their ability to work and their productivity because of the associated anemia. In 1953 the Ankylostoma section of the directorate of the institute of endemic diseases examined 8666 stool samples and found 39999 of them infected with Ankylostoma and other worms such as *Ascaris* and *Trichuris*.⁽²⁷⁾

Cholera, plague, and small pox were the most feared epidemic diseases during the evolution of healthcare in Iraq. However, only 10 of cholera cases were reported in Umara during the period from 1945 to 1948.⁽¹⁸⁾ The Iraq government made health restrictions on visitors from the neighboring countries (Iran, Jordan Syria, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia) and other countries such as India, Sudan, Indonesia

during epidemics of communicable diseases such as cholera.^(18,31) In addition the government tried to prevent small pox by vaccination. Despite vaccinations 2 epidemics occurred in Iraq, 1740 cases were registered in 1948 while during the second epidemic which begun in September 1956, 1948 in 1956 and 1942 in 1957. The second large epidemic was brought first to Erbil in the North of Iraq by Kurdish clan moving between Iran and Iraq to spread to the whole country.^(11, 25, 28)

Other important diseases in Iraq included typhoid fever, dysentery meningitis, and leprosy. Several epidemics of typhoid fever occurred in Iraq during the period from 1946 to 1955. In 1955 there was a large scale epidemic that spread to the whole country (721 in Baghdad, 152 in Dileim Liwa, and 130 in Mosul) with 2073 cases registered (41.5/ 100.000 population). 245 deaths (12%) were registered during the first epidemic.⁽²⁸⁾

Meningitis was during all months of the year with peak rate during the period from December to March. 3 epidemics of meningitis occurred in Iraq during the period from 1946 to 1956.⁽²¹⁾ 253 cases of meningitis were registered during the first meningitis epidemic in 1946 (5.4 cases/ 100.000 population). 306 cases of meningitis were registered during the second meningitis epidemic in 1954 (6.2 cases/ 100.000 population). 1252 cases of meningitis were registered during the third and largest meningitis epidemic in 1956 (50.4 cases/ 100.000 population).⁽²⁹⁾

Dysentery was very common among peasants because of the lack of poor water supply in rural areas.⁽²⁵⁾ The number of registered cases of dysentery per 100.000 populations during the period from 1946 to 1954 is shown in Table-6.⁽²⁹⁾

The high incidence of leprosy in the south of Iraq led the government to establish a leprosy health institution in Al -Umara. Table-7 shows the number of cases who were admitted to the institution during the period from 1953 to 1957 and the mortality rate during this period.⁽²⁵⁾

Anthrax was registered in the highest numbers in 1953 with 196 registered cases and in 1954 with 192 registered cases. 68 cases of anthrax were registered in 1955.⁽²⁹⁾

The highest incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis was registered in children between 4-10 years during the year 1950 with 10433 cases compared with 7476 in 1949.⁽¹⁶⁾

Many disorders especially communicable diseases such as gastroenteritis, dysentery, measles, mumps, whooping cough, neonatal tetanus, diphtheria and poliomyelitis were prevalent in Iraq in addition to malnutrition and anemia. Poor midwifery practices especially cutting the umbilical cord of the newborn with contaminated tools lead to death of many neonates with neonatal tetanus.⁽²¹⁾ The number of registered cases of poliomyelitis per 100.000 population is shown in Table-6.

Progress in Health care and health education: The three decades of the 1920s, 1930s, and 1940s witnessed the evolution of the administrative structure of the health care and health education. However, the number of hospitals and health institutions remained inadequate. During the 1950s the number of hospitals increased from 89 hospital in 1952 to 122 hospitals in 1957 while the number of clinics increased from 391 in 1952 to 487 in 1957.⁽²⁵⁾

Table(5): The numbers of the registered cases of the important endemic diseases in Iraq during the 1940s and 1950s

Year	Malaria [19]	Bilharzias [20-23]	Trachoma [25,26]	TB [28]	Syphilis [29]	Soft[29] chancere	GC [29]	Ankylostoma Infection[26]
1946	742921	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1947	717841	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1948	603698	24272	524940	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1949	492602	27388	510118	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	10754
1950	537286	23372	507214	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	9518
1951	456299	35287	577511	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	16188
1952	409075	32672	118403	N/A	999	5954	11532	23686

1953	451132	29249	489527	11774	9169	764	4402	19167
1954	330623	37784	414844	14811	7640	445	3313	23727
1955	220926	42495	406616	13034	N/A	N/A	N/A	24035
1956	217834	54669	431245	15919	N/A	N/A	N/A	24035
1957	107204	56347	346110	13808	N/A	N/A	N/A	24876
1958	N/A	N/A	349315	10840	N/A	N/A	N/A	23226

Table (6): The number of registered cases of dysentery and poliomyelitis per 100.000 population during the period from 1946 to 1955.

Year	Dysentery: number of cases /100.000 population [29]	Poliomyelitis: number of cases /100.000 population [31]
1946	268.5	0.36
1947	300.2	0.68
1948	306	1.6
1949	336	1.9
1950	326.6	1
1951	386.6	0.9
1952	426.5	1.8
1953	456.5	1.4
1954	305.5	1.5
1955	N/A	2.3

Table (7): The numbers of cases of leprosy who were admitted to the institution during the period from 1953 to 1957 and the mortality rate during this period.

Year	No of cases	M	F	Deaths	M	F
1953	47	38	9	10	6	4
1954	54	48	6	19	17	2
1955	32	29	3	8	7	1
1956	48	28	20	--	--	--
1957	64	52	12	24	19	5

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